

Date: _____

No: _____

V8

District Name: _____

Name of the Sector: _____

Incorporating residents' perspectives on human-wildlife conflict management to build community resilience in Chitwan National Park, Nepal.

Part 1: Status of resident's experience and their wildlife encounters

1. Do you or your family encounter any conflicts with wildlife in the past five years? Yes No
 - a) If **yes**, what damage? (1) Human casualty (2) Human injury (3) Livestock casualty (4) Livestock injury (5) Crop damage (6) Property damage (7) Others, _____
 - b) If **yes**, which wild species? (1) Elephant (2) Tiger (3) Rhinoceros (4) Deer (5) Leopard (6) Wild boar (7) Monkey (8) Crocodile (9) Gaur (10) Others, _____
2. Have you applied compensation for the above mentioned losses? Yes No
 - a) If **yes**, any compensation is received for the above-mentioned losses? Yes No
 - b) If **yes**, are you satisfied with the compensation received for the losses? Yes No
3. Do you think getting compensated for losses is a lengthy process?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
4. Do you think HWC is increasing in recent years?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
5. Do you think building fences are an effective way to reduce HWC?
 - (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree
6. Do you think that compensation is an effective way to reduce suffering due to HWC? Yes No

Part 2: Residents' perceived importance and performance of HWC management

Degree of Importance					This section is meant to understand your level of awareness and perception of HWC management and the capacity of your resilience to adapt.	Degree of performance				
SU	U	N	I	SI		SD	D	N	A	SA
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	1. Basic skill development for livelihood diversification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Ability to secure resources through elected officials	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Strengthen HWC awareness through educational workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	4. Cultivation of economically viable buffer crops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	5. Accelerated compensation fund	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Diversify the livelihood opportunities for additional financial support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	7. Improve social bonding between the park management and residents	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	8. Strengthen working groups in each village to deal with HWC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 3: Socio-economic data

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Religion: (1) Hinduism (2) Buddhism (3) Kiratism (4) Christianity (5) Islam
(6) Others, _____
3. What is your cast & ethnicity: _____
4. Indigenous community: Yes No
5. Marital status: (1) Single (2) Married (3) Divorced (4) Widowed
6. Age: (1) 20-29 y/o (2) 30-39 y/o (3) 40-49 y/o (4) 50-59 y/o (5) > 60 y/o
7. Education level: (1) Didn't attend school (2) Primary school (3) Middle school (4) High school
(5) Higher Secondary School (6) Diploma (7) Undergraduate
(8) Graduate & higher
8. Occupation: (1) Farmer (2) Fisherman (3) Daily wager (4) Tour guide (5) Forest guard
(6) Private business (7) Others, _____
9. Monthly income: (1) ≤ NPR10,000 (2) NPR 10,001-15,000 (3) NPR 15,001-20,000
(4) NPR 20,001-25,000 (5) NPR 25,001-30,000 (6) > NPR 30,001
10. What is the main source of family income:
(1) Farming (2) Fishing (3) Daily wages (4) Tour guide (5) Forest guard
(6) Foreign remittance (7) Private business (8) Others, _____
11. Family size: (1) ≤3 members (2) 4-6 members (3) 7-9 members (4) ≥10 members
12. How many years has your family been living in this village: (1) ≤15 years (2) 16-30 years
(3) 31-45 years (4) 46-50 years (5) ≥60 years